

Views of Detainees for the Provision of Lyceum Education in the Closed Prisons of the Greek Territory

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Abstract: The education of all members of society is a prerequisite for the development of modern globalized society. Given this admission adult education and in particular, education of adults belonging to vulnerable social groups such as prisoners should be a particular concern. The various peculiarities of inmates increase the chances of their educational and by extension their exclusion. It is therefore imperative to provide educational programs that meet both their specific characteristics and the purpose of the custodial sentence. The initiative to operate an organized high school educational structure, for the first time in the Greek territory, within the 2nd Second Chance School (SCS) Prison School in Larissa and the absence of relevant surveys in Greece has led to an investigate both the views of prisoners – trainees on the structure for the provision of formal high school education in prisons and also the views of the education executives related to the incarcerated population. More specifically, the research objectives related to the views of education officers who are related to the training of prisoners in terms of the conditions of provision of high school education to prisoners, the role of the informal educational structure of high school level which operated inside the Court Prisons of Larissa as well as the factors that inhibit the prisoners' attendance in the second level of secondary education. At the same, the prisoners' expectations of attending high school were investigated and, in particular, the motivation to participate in the informal educational structure of SCS in the prisons of Larissa as well as the positive and negative elements of the operation of the structure. The methodological approach followed was that of qualitative research with a research tool, the semi – structured interview, on a sample of six individuals. The analysis of the findings has revealed the beneficial effect of attending structures of high school level on both the individual and on the community. However, given the existing conditions, the willingness of the internees acquire to high school education is made more difficult and any effort to provide high school education to prisoners is confronted with insurmountable impediments. Among the inhibitors of high school education of the prisoners were the conditions of detention, the insufficiency of prison time allotted for this purpose, the level of knowledge of the Greek language and the absence of a specific program tailored to the characteristics and needs of the detainees and in harmony with the aim of correction and the (re)integration of the prisoner. The above – mentioned research findings are in agreement with corresponding findings from the review of the relevant bibliography and could be a perpetual advisor and guide for anyone who researches and deals with the education of the vulnerable social group of prisoners.

Keywords: Prisoners, Typical Education, Lyceum Education, Vulnerable Social Groups, Informal School, Adult Education, Closed Prisons

1. Introduction

Each state shapes and adopts their prison system based on social cultural and religions concepts. Greece's prison system is organized on the basis of general principles of the Constitution, of the International Conventions, of the Laws and Presidential Decrees as well as of the regulatory acts delegated to the fundamental law by the applicable Penitentiary Code (Law 2776/1999). The lawfulness and equality of treatment of prisoners, which are

recognized by law, and their legal protection (Ministry of Justice, Transparency and Human Rights, 2017) are inviolable principles when applying the rules on the enforcement of sentences and security measures against freedom imposed by the competent courts.

2. Institutional framework for the operation of Prisons

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According to the Article 1 paragraph two of the Penitentiary Code, “detainees are considered to be persons serving sentences against Freedom..., as well as persons under detention and detained...”. More specifically, as referred to in The Rules of Operation of General Detention facilities Type A’ and B’ (M.D.58819/7.4.2003 Gov B’ 463/17.4.2003), “detainees” are considered to be the ones who are serving time or security measure against freedom, the in custody untried (prisoners or provisional prisoners), or prisoners for debts or for other purposes in execution of civil court decision, debtors of financial penalty, independently or by conversion or fine or court expenses and the “remaining”. “Remaining” plaintiffs “ are foreigners who, after their release, remain detained until their legal expulsion or until granted residence permit in the country due to improper deportation.

The detention centers are divided into: a) special detention centers for adults – rural prisons, b) special detention centers for young people, c) treatment outlets d) closed prisons. The closed prisons operating in the Greek territory are 24 in total, one of which is the detention facility of Larissa.

The Ministry of Justice in Transparency for the design and implementation of the country’s general punitive policy with the aim of as much as the rehabilitation and social reintegration of those who commit delinquent behavior and the development of acts of crime prevention (A.1, P.D.36/2000).

Within the framework of the modernization of the Greek prison system, prison detention is to be de-constrained by the separation of detainees according to their legal status, the ages, of the type and magnitude of the sentence being punished, and the training and professional training of detainees (Koulouris, 2009; Kelidou 2011). The prisoner is treated as a “subject of justice” (O.J.E.U., 2008) and the state has to support, through the prison and social policy, which it applies his reintegration after his release (Jiovanonglou, 2006; Kelidou, 2011).

However, critical views are expressed as to the correspondence of the intentions of the political power with the exercise of the prison policy in our country (Koulouris, 2008; Panousis, 2008), and the punitive nature of the Greek prison system (Margaritis & Parskevopoulos, 2005), as instead of limiting the marginalization of the detainees it is intensified. Also, despite the announcement of state initiatives to modernize the prison system, the social reintegration of detainees is considered to be an “unfulfilled goal” (Ombudsman, 2006) and the authorities themselves present their actions to the Council of Europe Committee for the Prevention of Torture and Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or

Punishment, which is responsible for auditing, in an accountable manner (Kelidou, 2011; Koulouris, 2009).

3. The need to train adult prisoners

From the 18th century until the middle of the 20th century, there was a predominant view that learning the Bible, in the context of prison education, would help both to reduce the illiteracy of the detainees and to morally reform them by giving a religious character to the education in prisons (Gerber & Fritsch, 1983).

However, some argue that education in prison (by the international term Prison or Inmate or Correctional Education) creates nothing but “better educated criminals” (Wikipedia, 2013). Against these skeptical voices are the voices of many researchers with particular remarkable findings, which have been the reason for the institutionalized establishment of the prisoners’ right to education.

As Lipton et al (1975) point out prison education reduces the chance of relapse, improves the social skills of the trained prisoners and as a provider of education leads to the creation of a positive personality who will accept the evil he has committed and will realize that he should not repeat it (Lipton et al, 1975). Indeed, Allen (1988) proved that while 80% of the inmates relapsed when came out of prison only 25% of those who attended the prison school relapsed. Also through the knowledge that the prisoner will obtain such as the use of a computer or acquire the skills of an electrician or plumber he will be able to find a job and integrate.

Allen (1988) also notes that it was particularly important the fact that in some prisons, in the last six months of imprisonment, the prisoners began to work in apprenticeships inside and outside prisons while other programs helped them to obtain the appropriate proficiency or professional license, so as to be able to start a business immediately.

At the same time, educational programs are often creative and through work they can improve the quality of life of the detainees and also provide them with stimuli for their social reflection. This means that prison education is not only about the process of release but also about the role of detainees in prison.

In the enclave environment, the prisoner who participates in educational programs may feel that he has a window of freedom in this environment while at the same time re-acquiring a relationship with the outside world. In addition to this, prison education allows detainees to upgrade their personality, to have high self esteem and to be more optimistic in a particularly difficult environment (Alexiadi, 1989).

In 1990, Parker's research highlighted the fact that participation in educational programs increases the self-esteem of prisoner as well as social skills which makes them integrate smoothly into society after their release. Moreover, Kett's research (1995) indicates that lessons that improve writing certainly have a positive effect.

Also, as Margaritis and Paraskevopoulos (2000) point out, educational opportunities should be provided at each level of education, when requested by the prisoner, in order to achieve a transition from a prisoner, whose knowledge is very basic, to an educated and integrated citizen who can be incorporated after his release. For this reason, the education of prisoners should be a priority of a system of education and management of prisons. The end result will be a prisoner who, when released, will be able to have basic skills which he will use in his everyday life. Apart from the inclusion of former prisoners in the labor market, the training of prisoners reduces the risk of social exclusion as we must not forget that it can be a factor in avoiding the case of the prisoner's engaging with the criminal mechanism. At this point, it should be noted that it is particularly important to have clear divisions between the educational and prison structures. Training must be done in a way that ensures the confidence of prisoners and it does not have the image of coercion and supervision. So freedom of choice should be a prerequisite for a successful training program for prisoners (Margaritis & Paraskevopoulos, 2000).

Harlow (2003) reports that as training programs for prisoners become more and more specialized, the likelihood of the occurrence of delinquent acts is diminishing. However, a particular detail is emphasized as Vacca (2004) states that in order for a training program for prisoners to be effective, it must be tailored to the needs of the population. This means that special attention should be paid to the identification of needs and the creation of a training program tailored to the particular needs of the trainee.

Also, as Dimitrouli et al quote (2006:201), "through education the prisoner can create a new reality...in every activity in which the inside communicates with the outside there is a dimension of shelter...it transforms stress, anxiety, stereotypes, undifferentiated the fear of symbols, into meaning, structure, limitation, maturity, responsibility". Through this process "he learns, creates choices and he can support them" (Dimitrouli et al, 2006:201). The prisoner understands what he lives and feels by turning the field of education into a "psychic space" and making his personal experiences a source of learning.

According to Aloskofis (2013) the chances of smooth reintegration or integration are increased, when the ex-prisoner during his imprisonment participated in therapeutic programs, in constructive activities (training, artistic expression) and maintained contacts with family and friends.

And all this while International research by the International Observatory on Prison Education has shown the generally lower level of education of prisoners compared to the average education in their country (Wacquant, 2002).

Regarding the effectiveness of prison training programs to reduce relapse, surveys conducted in the US and Canada show a reduction in the likelihood of relapse of prisoners who completed their education in prison (Behan as referred at Vergidis, Asimaki, & Tzintzidis, 2007) whereas obtaining an Equivalent General Diploma (high school level) in jail seems to have a positive effects on male prisoners and especially on women (Brewster & Sharp, 2002).

In the light of the implementation of policies in the member – states of the council of Europe, which recognize the link between education and prison policy, the Report of the Council of Europe on prison education highlights the role of mobilizing detainees to participate in educational programs, given the causal link between the lack of mobilization of detainees with previous experiences at school and elsewhere (Conseil de l' Europe, 1990).

Following the Lisbon Strategy (2000 - 2009) the Council of Europe has adopted the "Europe 2020" strategic framework (2010 – 2020) for European Union Member States' cooperation in the field of Education and Training by focusing on knowledge – based development and the elimination of exclusions (Eur – lex, 2017).

Given the global economic recession and consequently the economic crisis and the sharpening of the global competition, Member States are invited to work together to support the farther development of education and training systems. The ultimate aim is to ensure: a) the personal social and professional development of all citizens and b) the economic prosperity and employability while promoting democratic principles, social cohesion, active citizenship and intercultural dialogue (Official Journal of the European Union, 2009).

Among the main goals of every Member State is to increase the participation of the crucial age group 25-64 in life learning programs to at least 15% and to 40% the percentage of people aged 30-34 with a tertiary education level.

The centralized Greek system with the intense state interference and the socio – economic structures of the Greek structure concomitant with the Greek educational system’s inability to follow the pace of the development of the education systems of the countries of the European Union have been reflected over time in OECD (OECD, 1995; OECD, 2011), where it is said that “ Greece remains one of the most centrally- funded education systems in Europe”. The ineffectiveness of the attempted reforms in the country could be linked to the short duration of the term of office of ministers passing through the ministry of education (for a mere one and a half year from the post – modernization period until today), and the subsequent discontinuity of the education policy. At the same time, it is worth pointing out that in the tug of quantity and quality, in Greece the educational policy is characterized by an end in the absorption of resources from the European funds with a loss of efficiency in the reforms and thus in linking education and training with the modernization of the society and the economy (Panitsidis, 2008). As a consequence, the centralized bureaucratic model and corporative perceptions become inhibiting factors in initiating and implementing reforms to meet the priorities of the “European tools”, which it promotes.

According to a survey by Panitsidis and Papastamatis, the main reform axes for the Greek educational system to be able to follow International development, concern the decentralization of competences and the autonomy of school units in the development of a culture evaluation, a combination of education and the labor market, the cultivation of culture of Lifelong Learning and in the flexibility of the curricula (p. 356).

4. Legal framework of post – compulsory secondary education

According to the Greek education system in force and the system of initial vocational training for public free education and post – secondary education, it is possible, by individual choice, to continue studying in General High School (Day or Evening) or a Vocational School (V.S.) or a Vocational Training School (V.T.S.). The post – graduate degree certificate is a High School (level 4, according to Law 4283/2014), Degree of Specialization (level 4) and Degree of Specialty (level 3) of an equivalent level.

The fields and specialties of the Vocational Schools (VS) and the correspondence between them were determined by the law 4386/2016 (A’ 83) (Gov 1489/2016).

Prisoners may attend secondary education training programs by falling under the category of individually – taught students and they can take

qualifying examinations. The provisions E1/550/4.5.1982 (B’296), E3/96/22.2.1985 (B’ 105), Γ2/3031/22.10.1985 (B’726), Γ2/3560/25.9.1989 (B’720) of the decisions of the Minister of Education and Religious Affairs and the provisions of the first paragraph of the fourth paragraph of Article 46 of the law 2413/1996 (124 A’) define the categories of students for whom it is particularly difficult to attend the program of day and evening general and vocational lyceums and may be included in the category of individually - taught students. The imprisoned are also included in this category. As far as the vocational high schools are concerned, with a new provision, which was voted and notified on 30-6-2017 (Protocol number 107225/Δ4) by the Head of the Department of Vocational education of the Ministry of Education, only the students of first grade of vocational high schools can be characterized as individually – taught students.

In the case of temporary imprisonment the enrollment of students in the category of individually – taught, a certificate proving their imprisonment is required. The individually – taught students are required to submit to the school – high school the aforementioned certificate and the relevant application at least 10 days before the end of the 2nd semester.

Then the school head will chair a three – member committee of two teachers of the same or related to the specialty course and will hold a qualifying examination of the individual – taught student (P.D. 465/1981 article 8), examinations i e promotional or graduating which are conducted in writing and orally. The Presidential Decree 465/1981, sets out the procedures for conducting the examinations.

During the school year 2015-2016 seven graduates of the 2nd Second Chance Scholl (SCS) of Larissa were enrolled in the first class of the Evening general High School of Larissa and were promoted to the second class of High School. Their effort was met with success thanks to the “volunteer school” which operated in a room of the 2nd SCS of Larissa (Prisons). The detainees were enrolled in the Evening General High School of Larissa, but according to the law they had to study alone in their cell and at the end of the school year to take exams as individual - taught students. Having apprehended the need to help these pupils, the leaders of Larissa Prisons turned to the implementation of a pilot training program. They organized an informal high school classroom in a prison room where on a daily basis volunteer on teachers taught in the Evening General High School in order to stand assists in the struggle of the prisoners – students and their will to learn. With the support of the prison administration but also thanks to

the examiners of the Evening General Lyceum who went to the prison to examine the students orally and on writing, the “voluntary school even helped two of the prisoners students to achieve excellence of progress. During the next school year 2016 – 2017, it was not possible for them to continue their studies since being registered in the Second Class of VS in the Department of Administration and Economics they were not allowed to be admitted to the category of individually – taught students and there was no concern to remove this obstacle.

However, new horizons and prospects for the training of the detainees are being opened in February 2016 by Law 4386/2016 (Gov A’ 21/21-2-2016), as individual teaching provided to prisoners is covered by Article 26 paragraph 1a in the sense of “compensatory education”, aimed at reintegrating pupils into the learning process to reduce school dropout rates and improve their performance in order to complete compulsory education and to increase access or completion rates of secondary education and the enhancement of prospects of access to tertiary education.

According to paragraph 2 of the same article, “compensatory education” programs in the framework of individual teaching in prison are carried in detention centers.

The Regional Director of Primary and Secondary Education is the one who decides on the educational problems related to the planning and implementation of the individual teaching of detainees, after taking into account the opinion of the competent Adviser of Education of Detainees or by lack of whom he will take into account the opinion of the others designated by the law (Law. 4386/2016, article 26, paragraph 5).

The cost of the individual training of detainees in the detention centers will be covered by co-funded programs.

The Competent Regional Director of Primary and Secondary Education in the case of the individual – teaching of prisoners in the detention facilities draws up a special list of teachers, according to the criteria provided by a decision of the Minister of Culture, Education and Religion. Permanent, temporary substitute teachers and hourly teachers are recruited according to this list (Law 4386/2016, article 26, paragraph 9) and their remuneration is determined by joint decision of the Minister of Culture, education and Religious Affairs and the Minister of Finance (Law 4386/2016, article 26, paragraph 12).

4. Empirical Survey

4.1. Purpose and objectives of the survey

The purpose of the survey was to investigate the views of adult prisoners in prisons about High school education and in particular those who attended the informal educational structure “hosted” in the 2nd SCS prison of Larissa during the school year 2015-2016. The individual objectives referred to the expectations and incentives for the participation of prisoner in a high school education program as well as the positive and negative characteristics of the educational structure that worked in this context. Among the objectives was also to record the views of the educational staff on the conditions and organization for the provision of high education to the incarcerated population.

4.2. Research questions

In order to achieve the aim and objectives of the research, research questions were formulated concerning the aspirations of the detainees from attending “high school” the motivation to participate in the informal educational structure of the SCS prison of Larissa as well as on the positive and negative elements of the operation of the structure. In order to investigate the views of the education staff related to the prisoners’ education, the research questions concerned the conditions for the provision of high school education to detainees in the role of the informal high school level educational structure that functioned within the judicial prisons of Larissa as well as the factors that inhibit the attendance of the prisoners in high school.

4.3 Research Methodology

4.3.1. Design and conduct of research

The research was conducted in the spring of 2017. It is won a retrospective survey based on a qualitative methodology. The methodological tool for collecting the data was the semi - structured interview. Among the main questions, additional information was inserted for the sake of clarity and clarification. The sample was selected by deliberate sampling. In particular, of the nine initially trained prisoners in the Larissa Judicial Prisons, who began to attend the informal educational structure in the school year 2015-2016, the four dropped out.

Of the five, who continued and were promoted and who, according to the original plan, would potentially be studied, the two were released and one was transferred making it impossible to communicate with them. The two remaining prisoners in the Judicial Prison of Larissa at the time of the investigation and given that the informal educational structure did not work during the school year 2016-2017 constituted the sample of the survey. At the

same time all, related to the provision of formal education to adult prisoners during the school year 2015-2016, senior managers of the secondary education of the prefecture of Larissa as well as the two trainers in the structure constituted a sample of the survey. The research material was organized using the content analysis method (Creswell, 2011). The presentation of the results and the drawing of the conclusions were based on the dialectical relationship between the empirical research and the bibliographic review.

4.3.2. Sample Identity

The two respondents – detainees came from a Balkan country other than Greece. O LEO belonged to the age category between 31 and 35 years and MONTI in the 26-30 age group. Prior to his imprisonment, LEO was engaged in construction work while MONTI in electrical work. Both of them graduated from SCS of Prisons of Larissa.

Both trainers were female, retired secondary school teachers and offered volunteer work in the educational structure. The directors were men and they dealt with formal education structures.

4.3.3. Research constraints

The research was carried out in a detention facility in Larissa and a small sample of detainees. This has the effect that its results cannot be generalized for all prisoners in all prisons in the territory.

5. Key findings of the survey

5.1. The views of prisoners – trainees

The research subjects link the monitoring of the informal high school structure of the prisons with the formation of their personality and the professional perspective and emphasize their sociopolitical function (Parker, 1990; Jet, 1995; Dimitrouli et al., 2006; Aloskofis, 2013). In the conscious motivations of high school education mentioned above by both interviewees, “cognitive and professional ambitions” were included.

The need to learn the Greek language and the acquisition of a recognized certificate in order to “open up career prospects” was highlighted (Allen, 1988; Parke, 1990; Margaritis & Paraskevopoulos, 2000). Both of them understood that in the competitive working reality education and specialization are demanded (Lipton et al., 1975; Allen, 1988; Jarvis, 2004). That is why, despite the generalized insecurity, they aimed at completing their high school education and continuing at their studies in tertiary education.

1. “To know... and get a paper to get a certificate. But most of all I would like to get, if there was,

any specialty. Most of all because I think it's better to have a specialty because you go somewhere and you serve somewhere. If you have a paper it is different”. [...] “Ok, if I was a good student I would like to go to high school but ok I am not and...” (MONTI).

2. “I didn't know the language, I didn't even know how to write or read, not even Greek [...]. I would like, if I was given the chance in prison to continue in the university too” (LEO).

It is worth noting, in both cases, the link between the acquisition of knowledge, and the empowerment of individuality (Lipton et al., 1975; Parker, 1990; Dimitrouli et al., 2006). The school is for the subject of research directly intertwined with both strengthening self – esteem and self- sufficiency as well as with their need for social upgrading and recognition.

3. “I see life differently, I feel more creative, whatever you can give while if you are in prison you fall behind in a few words. [...]. “I wanted to continue High school to learn something, to become a human being, because I am tired of being in prison” (LEO).

4. “As long as you are in prison you don't think about anything, that is... and when you think it's worse. Being in jail it is a tough thing. In the beginning, I went crazy, all the time in prison, no, I had to find something [...] “School helps you not to stay behind. Personally, because things were bad for me, since I went to school I gained confidence in a few words, I cursed myself [...] “So now, all I want is school. It is something good for you and society”. (MONTI)

Also prisoners linked their participation in educational programs and their study in high school with the management of the suffering that imprisonment involves (Alexiadi, 1989; Dimitrouli et al., 2006).

5. “...and I wanted to get out of their, to go through another door... [...] School for me is how can I say? (like your wings open and you fly?) and I leave. Because I feel free here.” [...] “What, it is paradise for me. How can I explain it...I am...” (LEO)
6. Different, I am different. It is something else, how can I say it, you get away, because being in jail is monotonous. I see life differently...” (MONTI).

In addition the participants highlighted the importance and assistance of the trainers in their response to the requirements of high school.

7. "With the teachers, because maybe something that I don't know, maybe...what does this mean? He helps you, he helps you to be better" (LEO).

8. "If you study alone you are kinda bored, I think, this is my opinion, you are kinda bored, how... but if you are with a teacher, he helps you, alone how? Only with the book?" (MONTI).

5.2. Views of education executing

All interviewees pointed out the existence of difficulties in running a prison structure to provide formal high school education to prisoners without, however, seeing obstacles inaccessible.

9. "I believe that it is a matter of will first, of the Teachers Association of the VS or of the Evening school or of any school, of the club, approval, application to the education department and the education department promotes the request to the ministry to create high school classes by decision of the ministry or a school appendix. We have attachments of such schools in youth prisons, it is not a new practice. It can be done, we have experience that in youth detention centers" (S3).

10. "In my opinion I think it is possible if there is a will from the prison administration. That is to allow convenient programs like that and school operation hours even in the afternoon [...]. I think it is a matter of who is in charge and how responsible he is and how much he is afraid to open up" (S2).

11. "People need something like that because there is a lack of it, but it is difficult to find a way to do it. I mean that we had a lesson in the library, it was just one class...It is difficult because prison operating hours are not flexible, and even if we had teachers, we wouldn't be able to have more classes" (S1).

Concerns have been expressed in particular, on the possibility of providing formal education to prisoners which are being opened by the adoption of the Law 4386/2016 on Compensatory Education.

12. "First of all we are not in favor of running classes of compensatory education, why? [...] it is not a permanent situation. We want a stable structure...Every year we have to prepare in time for its operation [...] We must also clarify the issues of the prison" (S3).

As to the role of the informal educational structure, in addition to the contribution of the structure to the trainee's response to the promotional examinations, the role of the structure in defending the right of the imprisoned population to education was stressed and the functioning of the structure was connected with the transformation of the perceptions, of the correction and the reintegration of the detainees.

13. [...] So, since first it is their right second it works in the context of correction and reintegration, I can not understand why we do not have it and why a structure like this does not exist" (S3).

14. "You have to open up their horizons so they can have an image of today's society, especially for the prisons. You have to change their opinion because they have this particular view that everybody is to blame except for themselves" (S2).

15. "Any activity, leaving his cell and opening a book is positive. It would be much better, if things were heading towards this direction, that is, if we always thought about that (...). Also, the prison should offer education to the inmates and you have to take this into account without reducing demands on people because it is a requirement that will bring them to a state of improvement and then they will be able to enjoy themselves...I think it is a consolation to connect him to the world of the book and civilization, you give him space to breathe, that is, he is in his cell but he is reading a book or he is thinking, he believes in himself that he can handle things and he can think about his future in another way. Also, this process supports him psychologically" (S1).

At the same time, it is critical and necessary for the majority of research subjects to apply the principles of adult education in adult prison educational programs. In particular, the role of empathy and active educational techniques is emphasized in fulfilling the participation of detainees in educational programs and in the transformation of perceptions that are directly and indissolubly linked to correction.

16. "Adult education is another thing, not that it has nothing in common but [...] You have to find ways to go to where you want to reach without pressing it. [...] Keeping in mind that the person is not tabula rasa and that he (the imprisoned) is in your hands having starts his day with a fight with the guard, for this empathy is required on the adult educator's part. I mean, you have to be able to consider the other person's feelings without lowering the level of education" (S1).

17. "What would be useful is the high school teachers who will come to educate the prisoners to have experience in adult education [...] This would protect both the educators and the trainees who are used to a different way of life" (S3).

Also the interviewees considered the detention conditions difficult for the detainees to meet the demands of the individual teaching on high school level.

18. "It is difficult. How can someone study when there are 10 people in the same cell." (S1). "It is difficult for the detainee to isolated in order to study,

as he does not have his own desk. The only things that exist are a desk and a tv in one room. There is no study area, there is no private room and of course there are other 5-8 people in the cell and when the cells open there is too much noise for them to concentrate” (S3).

In addition, the time allotted by the prison considered insufficient for the trainees to meet the requirements of the standard curriculum.

Also according to the general confession of the participants, that is documented by their personal experience, there are handles that are difficult to overcome especially in the case of foreign prisoners whose knowledge of the Greek language is too little to meet the requirements of formal high school let alone the requirements of the general and evening high school.

19. “With a special program yes. The Albanians attended Ancient Greek lessons....Of course you can’t start their teaching with the first chapter of Xenophon. Let’s not get carried away, of course. If you have to deal with someone whose language does not belong to the Indo – European language, you have a serious problem, because you do not know what you can compare it with so that you can make him understand. [...] There are serious difficulties that can be overcome only with a special program.” (S1)

20. “When you have to deal with people who do not know good Greek, it is pointless to teach them ancient Greek. Not even modern Greek much less ancient Greek. (...) It takes a lot of work, in terms of linguistics. A lot of hard work.” (S2)

21. “It is hard, even for the Greek detainee who has dropped out of school let alone a foreigner or a Roman [...]. Since they haven’t been taught ancient Greek in SCS and maybe they have come from a school abroad. It is not just difficult, it is impossible...” (S3).

6. Conclusions

Prison training is not only a need for prisoners but also a basic human right (Law 2776/1999). Legitimate and equal treatment of prisoners, respect for the rights of prisoners recognized by law and their legal protection (Ministry of Justice, Transparency and Human Rights, 2017) are inviolable principles when applying the rules on the enforcement of sentences and security measures against freedom, imposed by the competent courts. Every prisoner must have access to basic knowledge under equal and perhaps even better terms than those who are out of prison.

The Law 2525/97 establish the second – chance schools (SCS) which operate at a primary or

secondary level of education (Vergidis, 2008). The SCS operate even in closed prisons in the Greek territory, enabling prisoners to receive a high school certificate. However the desire and need of detainees to receive high school education is inhibited. Firstly, there are no statutory permanent formal education structures that can operate within detention facilities. Then the prospects for the training of detainees which opened up with the law 4386/2016 (Gov A’ 21/21-2-2016), with the possibility of implementing compensatory training programs in detention facilities in the context of individual teaching of detainees, are in a theoretical context, since the law has not yet been implemented, there are ambiguities and gaps in the law. The implementation of programs is not mandatory but depends on the training of the administrators of Education and Education of Detainees, while the cost of individual teaching of detainees in detention centers depends on co-funded programs. But let us not forget that the purpose of absorbing funds from European funds is damaging the effectiveness of the reforms (Panitsidis, 2008). At the same time, detainees may attend general or evening high schools falling under the category of individual – taught but the program does not take care to adapt the educational process to the profile and the needs of the vulnerable social group of prisoners (Vacca, 2004). Also, instead of the prison applying the intervention “tools” (Daskalaki, 1996) including the provision of school and vocational training with the ultimate aim of limiting the social exclusion of the prisoners, the inmates are deprived of their right to high school vocational training, as they are unable to attend second and third grade of Vocational High School (Arrangement with protocol Article 107225/D4 of the Ministry of Education and Religion) and to receive a certificate and at the same time a certified professional qualification. As a result, the Greek education system appears to be undertaking reforms that are at least not in line with the priorities of the “Europe 2020” strategic framework (Official Journal of the European Union, 2009).

Greece as a member state of the Council of Europe, given the economic downturn and the sharpening of global competition, is committed to ensuring the personal professional and social development of all citizens without exception and increasing the percentage of people with tertiary educational attainment (Euro-lex, 2017). The exclusion of detainees from their professional high school education deprives them of their ability and need to acquire knowledge and to upgrade their personality in order to create suitable conditions for their social integration and for their integration into the labor market (Allen, 1988; Parker, 1990; Margaritis & Paraskevopoulos, 2000).

Also the statements of the research subjects showed that living conditions in Greek prisons are too special and adverse for the prisoners to respond to the demands of High school education. Prison has the meaning of total forcible structure, the prisoner is treated as tabula rasa and is called to manage the “underculture” of prison which functions as it was declared as “people’s caretaker”. However, mostly, the prisoner will only spend a very specific amount of his life in prison. This means that there should be educational and training programs that will help him both cope with the difficulties in life in prison (Alexiadi, 1989) and transform his mental habits so that he can smoothly integrate into society when he is released. The adult prisoner needs to have a critical awareness of his or her own and others assumptions and expectations and to assess their relationship with the formulation of an interpretation. It is therefore necessary and advisable to engage the prisoner in a cognitive process of transformational learning. The trainer, having taken into account the characteristics of this social group and the fact that the expected subjective and objective re-filing is usually an intensely threatening emotional experience, is required to create a learning model such as that of critical thinking to “intervene” in the learner’s mind. The inmate needs to be critically thoughtful about his assumptions and their consequences in order to transform his mental habits. Involved in a learning process and with the assistance of the co-operating trainer and the active educational process, the prisoner will obtain at the time of his/her imprisonment the guarantees for his/her social (re)integration and will nullify the possibility of relapse.

In conclusion, we could support the view that if the transforming learning process within closed prisons is included in the high school education process, then the upgrading of the formal qualifications of the inmates is achieved as these qualifications are a necessary condition in the era of the advanced technology of the economic recession and of high cognitive requirements.

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